

Kinetics of hydrogenation of some terminal olefins catalyzed by anchored montmorillonitebipyridinepalladium(II) acetate

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Kinetics of hydrogenation of some terminal olefins conjugated to functional groups such as methyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate, ethyl acrylate, acrylic acid and acrylonitrile have been carried out by anchored montmorillonitebipyridinepalladium(II) acetate in THF medium. Under the reaction conditions, 100% saturation of carbon-carbon double bond has been observed and there is no polymerization. An attempt has been made to correlate functional groups and their ability to activate or deactivate C-C double bonds. The observed rate is first order with respect to partial pressure of hydrogen and fractional order with respect to both [catalyst] and [substrate]. The rate of hydrogenation follows the trend : methyl methacrylate > methyl acrylate > ethyl acrylate > acrylic acid > acrylonitrile. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated, and rate law and plausible mechanism have been proposed.

Preparation of the catalyst by immobilizing active transition metal complexes on solid supports such as organic polymers and inorganic oxides has been attracting wide spread attention in recent years¹. Serious interest in these catalysts originated with efforts to solve the problems associated with both homogeneous and heterogeneous systems, such as catalyst recovery. The new anchored catalysts have attractive features of being reproducible, allowing control and knowledge of the nature of the incipient species anchored on the support. Among the random inorganic oxide solid supports, clays were shown to be good catalyst supports. The clay support, used in this study was montmorillonite, a smectite clay. The montmorillonite possesses large amounts of highly reactive species. Various solvents can also swell the intra-crystalline space of the clay, and the degree of swelling depends upon the inter-layer cations, the substrate and negative charge density on the silicate sheet². Taking advantage of these features, many functional groups like bipyridine, diphenylphosphine, triphenylphosphine, amino groups and 4-picoline have been intercalated to the montmorillonite^{3,4}. Even

though mechanistic studies of hydrogenation of olefinic compounds were explored using these anchored catalysts⁵, very little attention has been diverted towards the kinetics of the reactions to understand the reaction pathways⁶⁻⁸. Therefore, in the present study a detailed investigation of hydrogenation of some structurally related terminal olefins, such as methyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate, ethyl acrylate, acrylic acid and acrylonitrile has been carried out by anchored montmorillonitebipyridinepalladium(II) acetate. The catalyst has been found to be very effective in hydrogenating the olefins without any isomerization or polymerization.

Results and Discussion

The variation of rates with change in substrate concentration (accuracy $\pm 4\%$) at three different temperatures in the range 288–306 K (accuracy ± 0.5 K) have been presented in Table 1. Fractional order with respect to [substrate] is indicated from the linear plots of $\log V$ vs $\log [S]$. The orders were found to be 0.46, 0.44, 0.39 and 0.53, respectively for methyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate,

Table 1. Effect of [substrate] on reaction rates at different temperatures

$10^2[S]$	Rate $\times 10^3$ mmol s ⁻¹														
	Methyl methacrylate			Methyl acrylate			Ethyl acrylate			Acrylic Acid			Acrylonitrile		
	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K
0.50	0.75	1.30	1.62	0.63	1.32	1.63	0.52	1.22	1.52	0.56	1.23	1.54	0.25	1.02	1.38
1.00	1.10	1.98	2.40	0.91	1.89	2.37	0.78	1.74	2.24	0.77	1.71	2.21	0.66	1.63	2.14
2.00	1.33	2.57	3.18	1.16	2.28	3.23	1.02	2.32	2.88	0.94	2.02	2.80	0.90	2.22	2.88
2.50	1.55	2.90	3.59	1.11	2.68	3.48	1.09	2.63	3.42	1.03	2.41	3.15	0.97	2.54	3.39
3.00	1.63	3.06	3.81	1.29	2.83	3.68	1.49	2.79	3.64	1.08	2.53	3.33	1.03	2.72	3.64
4.00	1.85	3.44	4.10	1.45	3.00	4.21	1.34	2.99	4.20	1.13	2.59	3.72	1.11	3.16	4.28

Reaction conditions : $[C] = 0.40 \times 10^{-2}$ mmol, $P_{H_2} = 1.063 \times 10^2$ k Nm⁻². Solvent : THF.

Table 2. Effect of [catalyst] on reaction rates at different temperatures

10 ² [C]	Methyl methacrylate			Methyl acrylate			Ethyl acrylate			Acrylic acid			Acrylonitrile		
	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K	288	300	306 K
0.20	0.80	1.35	1.58	0.66	1.30	1.58	0.56	1.23	1.51	0.56	1.19	1.43	0.47	1.13	1.39
0.25	0.90	1.55	1.73	0.74	1.48	1.82	0.63	1.34	1.69	0.61	1.36	1.70	0.54	1.26	1.59
0.30	0.98	1.59	2.04	0.81	1.56	2.11	0.69	1.47	1.93	0.65	1.45	1.89	0.59	1.36	1.87
0.40	1.12	1.96	2.39	0.94	1.88	2.39	0.76	1.76	2.26	0.78	1.73	2.19	0.68	1.66	2.17
0.50	1.20	2.18	2.72	0.99	2.11	2.63	0.84	2.11	2.50	0.85	1.88	2.52	0.71	1.83	2.41

Reaction conditions : [S] = 1.00 × 10⁻² mmol, p_{H₂} = 1.063 × 10² k Nm⁻². Solvents : THF.

ethyl acrylate, acrylic acid and acrylonitrile. With increase in catalyst concentration, rates were found to increase (Table 2). The plots of log V vs log [catalyst] revealed fractional order dependence on the [catalyst]. However, unit order was observed with respect to hydrogen partial pressure.

Based on the above data the following mechanism is proposed which is in accordance with the one proposed by Turkervich *et al.*⁹ for hydrogenation of ethylene in heterogeneous catalysis involving palladium, represented by

Scheme 1. Plausible mechanism for hydrogenation of acrylic acid.

eqs. (1)-(3) and Scheme 1. This is also in parallel with the mechanism proposed by Terasawa *et al.*⁶ and Nayak *et al.*⁷ for the hydrogenation of various olefins catalyzed by polymer bound palladium(II) complexes,

Thus the mechanism involves the initial complex (C₁) formation between catalyst (C) and hydrogen involving hydride ion transfer to the palladium, replacing acetate ion. In the second equilibrium step, initially olefin (S) forms a π-complex (C₂) with the palladium and simultaneous hydride ion transfer takes place from palladium to olefin. The last step is rate-determining which involves the transfer of proton to substrate leading to the separation of the hydrogenated product from the catalyst. Thus the catalyst is regenerated.

The rate law derived is as

$$V = \frac{dp}{dt} = k [C_2] \quad (4)$$

If *a* moles of catalyst 'C' and *b* moles of hydrogen participate in eqn. (1) and *x* moles of C₁ are formed under equilibrium conditions, the equilibrium constant *K*₁ can be written as

$$K_1 = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)} \quad (5)$$

If *a* >> *b*, i.e. [C] >> [H₂], then (a - x) ~ a.

Therefore, from eqn. (5),

$$K_1 = \frac{x}{a(b-x)} \text{ or } x = \frac{K_1 a b}{1 + K_1 a}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } [C_1] = \frac{K_1 [C][H_2]}{1 + K_1 [C]} \quad (6)$$

From eqn. (2), i.e. second equilibrium step, if *c* and *d* are the initial concentrations of complex [C₁] and [S], respectively, then under equilibrium conditions the resultant concentrations are (c - y) and (d - y), where y represents the concentration of complex C₂. Therefore, equilibrium constant *K*₂ is

$$K_2 = \frac{y}{(c-y)(d-y)} \quad (7)$$

If $d \gg c$, i.e. $[S] > [C_1]$, then $(d - y) \sim d$.

Therefore, from eqn. (7),

$$K_2 = \frac{y}{d(c-y)} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{K_2cd}{1 + K_2d}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } [C_2] = \frac{K_2[C_1][S]}{1 + K_2[S]} \quad (8)$$

Combining eqns. (6) and (8),

$$[C_2] = \frac{K_1K_2[C][H_2][S]}{(1 + K_1[C])(1 + K_2[S])} \quad (9)$$

Substituting the value of C_2 in eqn. (4),

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = V = \frac{kK_1K_2[C][H_2][S]}{1 + K_1[C] + K_2[S] + K_1K_2[C][S]} \quad (10)$$

This equation accounts for the first order dependence on [hydrogen] and fractional order with respect to [catalyst] and [substrate].

In order to evaluate the individual equilibrium and rate constants K_1 , K_2 and k , the eqn. (10) is modified in terms of k' , the pseudo-first order rate constant at constant [hydrogen] as

$$k' = \frac{V}{[H_2]} = \frac{kK_1K_2[C][S]}{1 + k_1[C] + K_2[S] + K_1K_2[C][S]} \quad (11)$$

Taking reciprocals of eqn. (11),

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[C][S]} + \frac{1}{kK_2[S]} + \frac{1}{kK_1[C]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (12)$$

K_2 is evaluated from the ratio of intercept and slope of the plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[S]$. Similarly, from the linear plots of $1/k'$ vs $1/[C]$, K_1 is evaluated. From the values of K_1 , K_2 and the intercept of plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[S]$, the rate constant k has been evaluated. The reactions were studied at different temperatures and the corresponding thermodynamic and activation parameters were evaluated (Tables 3 and 4). ΔG is negative for both equilibrium steps indicating the spontaneity of the complex formation. The entropy of activation for all the reactions have been found to be negative. This is due to compactness of the transition state as compared to the ground state causing restriction on the transitional and rotational freedom, thus reducing the entropies of the system. In order to know the nature of the reaction, the thermodynamic data and rate constants data have been cast into Leffler's and Exner's plots^{10,11}. A linear plot of ΔH^\ddagger as a function of ΔS^\ddagger indicates the isokinetic temperature to be 282 K. Similarly, a value of 280 K has been obtained from the linear plot of $\log k_{300}$ vs $\log k_{306}$. The value is below the experimental temperature range (288–306 K), indicating that the reactions are controlled by entropy factors.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters at 300 K involving equilibrium constants K_1 , K_2^*

Parameter	Methyl methacrylate	Ethyl acrylate	Methyl acrylate	Acrylic acid	Acrylonitrile
$-\Delta G$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	14.1 (11.2)	14.3 (11.5)	14.2 (11.1)	14.3 (11.7)	14.4 (10.5)
$-\Delta H$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	25.3 (14.4)	24.8 (16.8)	22.5 (15.0)	18.4 (15.7)	26.5 (15.63)
$-\Delta S$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	37.4 (10.4)	35.0 (17.6)	27.4 (13.0)	17.7 (13.2)	40.4 (17.1)

*Values in the parentheses calculated using K_2 .

Table 4. Activation parameters at 300 K*

Parameter	Methyl methacrylate	Ethyl acrylate	Methyl acrylate	Acrylic acid	Acrylonitrile
E_a^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	44.1	49.7	49.0	47.4	55.4
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	57.0	57.4	57.3	57.7	57.2
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	41.6	47.2	46.5	44.9	52.9
ΔS^\ddagger (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	51.3	34.0	35.9	42.9	14.5
10^5k (s ⁻¹)	7.3	6.3	6.6	5.5	6.8

*Values of k are presented at 300 K (accuracy $\pm 4\%$).

In all cases, none of the functional groups were hydrogenated. From Table 2 it can be concluded that the different functional groups affect the reaction rates according to the following series: COOMe > COOEt > COOH > CN. Thus, greater the electron density over the double bond, faster will be the reaction rate due to the favourable formation of palladium-olefin complex. The rates of hydrogenation of these terminal olefins are higher than the internal olefins¹⁰. The higher rates of terminal olefins is in parallel with relative stabilities of π -bonded Pd-olefinic intermediates towards olefin dissociation and also the predicted relative stabilities of the alkyl palladium intermediates formed from the corresponding olefins towards Pd-H elimination. The order of stabilities of alkyl palladium intermediates would be predicted to decrease in the order: n -alkyl complexes (from terminal alkenes) > n -alkyl complexes (from internal alkenes)¹². Thus overall rate seems to be largely influenced by electronic factors.

Experimental

Montmorillonite (1.2 meq g⁻¹) (Fluka), bipyridine and white silicone rubber septa (14 joint) (both Aldrich), palladium acetate (Alchem Laboratories) and n -butyl lithium (E. Merck) were used. All other chemicals were obtained from S.D. Fine Chemicals. Air and moisture-sensitive reactions were carried out in an inert atmosphere. All the reagents were either recrystallized or distilled wherever necessary by adopting standard methods¹³.

The catalyst was prepared according to the reported procedure⁴ and the hydrogenation reactions were carried out on a specially fabricated system¹⁴. Hydrogen was purified by passing over a deoxo catalyst, through molecular sieves and drying tubes before admission into the vacuum system.

Hydrogenation reactions were carried out in a 100-ml two-necked round bottomed flask. The side-arm was packed with a silicone rubber septa and the other arm to a glass vacuum manifold equipment with a manometer, a gas burette and a gas-inlet. To a weighed amount of the catalyst placed in the reaction vessel, dry THF (10 ml) was added and the whole system was evacuated and flushed three times with pure hydrogen. The mixture was shaken for 30 min in the presence of hydrogen. The weighed amount of substrate (olefin) in a measured quantity of solvent was injected into the pre-equilibrated reaction system. The shaking was carried out at such a speed to ensure that the reaction rate does not depend on shaking. Hydrogen uptake commenced without any induction period. The rate of hydrogen uptake was monitored at regular time intervals. At the end of each run, the catalyst was separated by filtration and washed with dry THF. The filtrate was spectroscopically analyzed (IR and NMR) for qualitative identification of the reaction products. To carry out the reactions at different temperatures, water was circulated through the outer jacket of the reaction system by using thermostat or cryostat.

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